

Synthesis of Bis-(phenyl/thienyl-sulphonyl)hydrazines

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During the course of study of physiological properties of 1-aryl/2-thienyl-sulphonyl hydrazones and 1-aryl/1-(2'-thienyl)sulphonyl 4-substituted thiosemicarbazides, various bis-(phenyl/thienyl-sulphonyl)hydrazines have been synthesised (Table I). A few bis-(phenylsulphonyl)hydrazines have been patented as photographic developers²⁻³; the absorption spectra of a few of these have been studied by Grammaticakis⁴.

TABLE I

Bis-(phenyl/thienyl-sulphonyl)hydrazines.
R₁.SO₂.NH.NH.SO₂.R'

R ₁ .	*M.P.	Formula.	% Sulphur.		% Nitrogen.	
			Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
A. R = Ph.						
C ₆ H ₅	228°	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ O ₄ N ₂ S ₂	20.4	20.5	8.9	9.0
<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	84°	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ O ₄ N ₂ S ₂	19.6	19.6	8.5	8.6
<i>p</i> -CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	260-62°	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ O ₅ N ₂ S ₂	18.6	18.7	8.0	8.2
<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	133°	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₂ ClS ₂	18.3	18.5	8.0	8.1
<i>p</i> -BrC ₆ H ₄	172-73°	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₂ BrS ₂	16.2	16.4	7.0	7.2
B. R = <i>p</i> -Tol.						
<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	222-24°(b)	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₂ S ₂	18.6	18.8	8.1	8.2
<i>p</i> -CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	240-42°	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ O ₅ N ₂ S ₂	18.0	18.0	7.7	7.9
<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	146°	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ O ₄ N ₂ ClS ₂	17.5	17.7	7.7	7.8
<i>p</i> -BrC ₆ H ₄	171-73°	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ O ₄ N ₂ BrS ₂	15.6	15.8	6.5	6.9
2-Thienyl	148°	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ O ₄ N ₂ S ₃	28.5	28.9	8.1	8.4
2-(5-Chlorothieryl)	244-46°	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₂ ClS ₃	26.0	26.2	7.3	7.6
2-(5-Bromothieryl)	254-57°	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₂ BrS ₃	23.2	23.4	6.5	6.8
C. R = <i>p</i> -anisyl.						
<i>p</i> -CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	247-49°	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ O ₅ N ₂ S ₂	17.0	17.2	7.2	7.5
<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	149°	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ O ₄ N ₂ ClS ₂	16.8	17.0	7.2	7.4
<i>p</i> -BrC ₆ H ₄	252-54°	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ O ₄ N ₂ BrS ₂	15.0	15.2	6.7	6.7
2-Thienyl	220-22°	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ O ₃ N ₂ S ₃	27.4	27.6	7.9	8.0
2-(5-Chlorothieryl)	246-47°	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₃ N ₂ ClS ₃	24.8	25.1	7.1	7.3
2-(5-Bromothieryl)	249-50°	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₃ N ₂ BrS ₃	22.2	22.5	6.2	6.6

1. Munshi *et al.*, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1963, 1, 311, 318.

2. Woodward, U.S. P. 2,874, 533/1954; *Chem. Abst.*, 1960, 54, 15038.

3. Willems, D.R.P. 1,023,909/1958; *Chem. Abst.*, 1954, 48, 7465.

4. *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1953, 86.

TABLE I (contd.)

R.	*M.P.	Formula.	% Sulphur.		% Nitrogen.		
			Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.	
D. R = <i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄ .							
<i>p</i> -CN ₂ H ₄	142°	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ O ₄ N ₂ Cl ₂ S ₂	16.6	16.8	7.0	7.3	
<i>p</i> -BrC ₆ H ₄	157°	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ O ₄ N ₂ BrClS ₂	14.8	15.0	6.4	6.6	
2-Thienyl	Decomp. > 280°	C ₁₀ H ₈ O ₄ N ₂ ClS ₃	26.2	27.2	7.6	8.0	
2-(5-Chlorothieryl)	142-44°	C ₁₀ H ₈ O ₄ N ₂ Cl ₂ S ₃	24.5	24.8	7.0	7.2	
2-(5-Bromothieryl)	146-47°	C ₁₀ H ₈ O ₄ N ₂ BrClS ₃	22.0	22.2	6.2	6.5	
E. R = <i>p</i> -BrC ₆ H ₄ .							
<i>p</i> -BrC ₆ H ₄	179°	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ O ₄ N ₂ Br ₂ S ₂	13.3	13.6	5.8	6.0	
2-Thienyl	176°	C ₁₀ H ₈ O ₄ N ₂ BrS ₃	24.0	24.2	6.8	7.1	
2-(5-Chlorothieryl)	175°	C ₁₀ H ₈ O ₄ N ₂ BrClS ₃	22.2	22.2	6.3	6.5	
2-(5-Bromothieryl)	168°	C ₁₀ H ₈ O ₄ N ₂ Br ₂ S ₃	20.0	20.2	5.6	5.9	
F. R = 2-Thienyl.							
2-Thienyl	101-102°	C ₈ H ₈ O ₄ N ₂ S ₄	39.0	39.5	8.2	8.6	
2-(5-Chlorothieryl)	99-101°	C ₈ H ₇ O ₄ N ₂ ClS ₄	35.6	35.7	7.5	7.8	
2-(5-Bromothieryl)	99°	C ₈ H ₇ O ₄ N ₂ BrS ₄	31.7	31.8	6.7	7.0	
G. R = 2-(5-Bromothieryl).							
2-(5-Chlorothieryl)	113-14°	C ₈ H ₆ O ₄ N ₂ BrClS ₄	29.0	29.2	6.2	6.4	
2-(5-Bromothieryl)	99-101°	C ₈ H ₆ O ₄ N ₂ Br ₂ S ₄	26.3	26.6	5.5	5.8	

Note. (a) Hinsberg (*Ber.*, 1894, 27, 601) and Curtius and Lorenzen (*J. prakt. Chem.*, 1898, *ii*, 58, 174) report m.p. 228°.

(b) Jennings (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 1172) reports m.p. 219-20(d), whereas Yoshida (Japan pat. 5767/1960; *Chem. Abstr.*, 1961, 55, 7359) report m.p. 172°.

*All melting points are uncorrected.

Symmetrical and unsymmetrical bis-(phenyl/thienyl-sulphonyl)hydrazines were prepared by the action of aryl/thienyl-sulphonyl chlorides on the corresponding aryl/thienyl-sulphonylhydrazines. Aryl/thienyl-sulphonyl chlorides were prepared by the method described in the literature⁵⁻⁶. Aryl/thienyl-sulphonylhydrazines, required for the condensation, have been synthesised by the action of hydrazine monohydrate on the corresponding aryl/thienyl-sulphonyl chlorides according to Albert *et al.*⁷. Synthesis of aryl/thienyl-sulphonylhydrazines has been reported earlier¹.

A typical method for the synthesis of bis-(phenyl/thienyl-sulphonyl)hydrazines is recorded below for all compounds described.

5. Morgan and Cretcher, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 375; Jackson and Frant, *ibid.*, 1955 77, 5625; Ullmann and Korzelt, *Ber.*, 1907, 40, 642; Steinkopf, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1927, *ii*, 117, 16; Harding, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 261.

6. Steinkopf *et al.*, *Annalen*, 1933 501, 178; 1934, 512, 136; 1937, 532, 250.

7. Albert and Royer, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 1150.

Symmetrical Bis-(2-thienylsulphonyl)hydrazine.—A mixture of thiophene-2-sulphonylhydrazine hydrochloride (2.14g., 0.01*M*) and thiophene-2-sulphonyl chloride (1.83 g., 0.01*M*) in ethanol (25 ml) was refluxed on a water bath for 4 hours. The resulting solution was filtered; the filtrate on evaporation yielded a crystalline product. This was recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 101-102°, yield, 1.1 g. (33%). One crystallisation was found to be satisfactory in most of the cases.

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